

IMPACT OF PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 3 PUPILS

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the relationship between parental involvement and the academic performance of Grade 3 pupils at Old Kibawe Elementary School. A quantitative research design was utilized to analyze the association between parental engagement and students' academic achievement. The respondents consisted of 24 Grade 3 pupils and their parents. Data were collected through survey questionnaires and students' academic records. Pearson's correlation coefficient and paired sample t-test were used to analyze the data. Results revealed a very strong positive correlation between parental involvement and academic performance ($r = 0.913$). However, the relationship was not statistically significant ($p = 0.087$). Additionally, demographic variables such as age, sex, attendance, and family income showed no significant difference in relation to academic performance. The findings suggest that while parental involvement contributes to students' learning experiences, other factors such as instructional strategies and classroom environment may also influence academic achievement. Further research with larger samples is recommended.

Keywords: *Parental involvement, Academic performance, Elementary education, Student achievement*

INTRODUCTION

The academic performance of students has long been a central focus in the field of education. Among the numerous factors influencing student success, parental

involvement has emerged as a critical determinant. Parental involvement refers to the participation of parents in their children's educational journey, including activities such as helping with homework, attending parent-teacher meetings, and creating a supportive home environment for learning. Fan & Chen (2001), parental involvement has a significant positive relationship with students' academic achievement, indicating that children perform better in school when parents actively participate in their education.

Grade 3 pupils are at a pivotal stage in their academic journey. By the third grade, students transition from "learning to read" to "reading to learn," marking a crucial period for cognitive and academic development. At this stage, parental involvement can be instrumental in shaping a child's academic trajectory. Supportive parental behaviors, such as reading together, fostering critical thinking, and encouraging problem-solving, enhance students' learning experiences and outcomes. Henderson and Mapp (2002), found that students whose parents are actively engaged in their education tend to earn higher grades, attend school more regularly, and demonstrate better attitudes toward learning. Parental involvement has been understood widely as something necessary for achieving student success at a child's learning level. Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler (1997), explained that parents become involved in their children's education when they believe that their participation can positively influence their child's learning and academic success.

Emphasized that parental involvement, including monitoring schoolwork and communicating with teachers, contributes positively to students' academic outcomes across different grade levels (Jeynes, 2012). Such children display higher motivation, better classroom behavior, and increased reading and mathematics skills. Conversely, other research emphasizes the importance of the frequency and quality of parental involvement. Revealed that parental involvement plays a vital role in improving students' academic performance, particularly when parents support learning activities both at home and in school (Castro et al. ,2015).

Despite the intuitive appeal of such benefits, the relationship between parental involvement and academic performance is subject to debate as to whether it improves academic performance per se or simply correlates with other factors, such as socioeconomic status or parental education levels. This study's findings are consistent with this perspective: there is a strong relationship between parental involvement and academic performance, but no evidence of causation.

Research studies on age and academic achievement generally conclude that age is an insignificant predictor on its own when it comes to academic achievement. According to the Theory of Cognitive Development by Piaget, it is evident that the intellectual level of children does not vary noticeably at the same developmental stage considering the age difference that is a month or two. However, various studies indicate maturity can impact areas such as comprehension in reading as well as problem solving (Cameron et al., 2015).

The influence of sex on academic performance has been a subject of considerable research. In general, there is an argument that boys tend to do well in math and science while girls excel in reading and language arts. This trend might be seen from the research done by Duckworth and Seligman (2006). But again, differences are mostly very slight, and often societal expectation and gender roles may contribute to such tendencies.

Attending school every day is commonly linked to success in class, since the more frequent students attend school the more chances, they have of having time to explore the lesson material and accomplish assigned work. Sirin (2005), higher family income enables access to better educational resources, such as private tutoring, books, and technology. Additionally, children from wealthier families may experience less stress related to financial instability, contributing to better academic performance. Socioeconomic status (SES) contributes to educational outcomes, affecting access to resources and exposure to learning opportunities (Hasl et al., 2019).

Research Questions

This study sought to determine the impact of parental involvement on the academic performance of Grade 3 pupils of Old Kibawe Elementary School as measured by their average grade and first quarter and second quarter assessments.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Sex.
 - 1.3 Grade level
2. What is the academic level of Grade 3 pupils of Old Kibawe Elementary School?
3. What is the extent of parents' involvement and access to resources in terms of:
 - 3.1. Help with homework;
 - 3.2. Attendance in school meetings;
 - 3.3. Parents' participation in school activities;
 - 3.4. Number of books at home;
 - 3.5. Internet access;
 - 3.6. educational materials used at home?
4. Based on the output of the study, what possible output can be developed?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quantitative research design, utilizing Pearson's r correlation analysis to examine the relationship between parental involvement and the academic performance of Grade 3 pupils at Old Kibawe Elementary School. Quantitative research was chosen because it enables the objective measurement of variables and the determination of statistical relationships between them. Specifically, the study

investigated how parental involvement and selected socio-economic factors influence learners' academic outcomes.

The research focused on variables such as family income, parental education, access to learning resources, and the level of parental participation in school-related activities. These variables were analyzed in relation to pupils' academic performance, as reflected in their quarterly grades. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the degree of parental involvement and learners' academic achievement.

The study aimed to provide empirical evidence on how parental participation and socio-economic conditions contribute to the educational success of elementary pupils. The findings were expected to help teachers, school administrators, and parents better understand the importance of parental engagement in improving academic performance.

Collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to ensure systematic and objective interpretation. Frequency and percentage were employed to describe the demographic profile of respondents and to present the distribution of parental involvement in school-related activities (Table 1). The mean was used to determine the overall level of parental involvement based on survey responses. To examine the relationship between parental involvement and pupils' academic performance, Pearson's r correlation coefficient was applied, as it is suitable for determining the strength and direction of association between two variables. Furthermore, a paired sample t -test was conducted to identify significant differences in academic performance when pupils were grouped according to demographic factors such as age, sex, attendance, and family income (Table 2).

These statistical tools were selected to provide a reliable and objective basis for data analysis and to ensure that the study's findings are supported by appropriate quantitative measures. The level of significance was set at 0.05 to guide the acceptance or rejection of the null hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study revealed a very strong positive correlation ($r = 0.913$) between parental involvement and the academic performance of Grade 3 pupils. This finding indicates that increased parental participation in school-related activities is associated with improved academic outcomes among learners. The correlation result was not statistically significant ($p = 0.087$). This suggests that while parental involvement may contribute positively to students' learning experiences, it cannot be considered the sole factor influencing academic achievement in this sample. Other elements such as instructional strategies, classroom environment, and individual learner characteristics may also influence academic performance.

The findings support previous studies indicating that parental involvement enhances students' learning motivation and academic engagement (Jeynes, 2012; Castro et al., 2015). Parents who monitor their children's schoolwork, communicate with teachers, and participate in school activities help create a supportive learning environment that promotes educational success. The results showed that demographic factors such as age, sex, attendance, and family income had no statistically significant difference in relation to academic performance. This implies that within the sample group, academic achievement was not strongly influenced by these demographic variables.

These findings suggest that while parental involvement remains an important component of student development, other educational factors should also be considered when improving students' academic performance.

Table 1. Frequency of Parental Involvement at School Activities

Correlation ▼

Pearson's Correlations

		Pearson's r	p
PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT	- ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE	0.913	0.087

Table 1. The Pearson's correlation ($r = 0.913$) shows a very strong positive relationship between parental involvement and academic performance, indicating that higher parental engagement is associated with better student achievement. However, the relationship is not statistically significant ($p = 0.087$), meaning it cannot be generalized with full confidence. Despite this, the high correlation suggests that promoting parental involvement may still have practical benefits for enhancing academic outcomes, and further studies with larger samples are recommended to confirm this relationship. The findings Xitao Fan (2001), indicated that parental engagement in school-related activities, such as assisting with homework and attending school meetings, is associated with higher levels of student academic success.

Table 2. The Significant Difference in the Demographic Factors Towards Level of Academic Performance.

Paired Samples T-Test

Measure 1	Measure 2	t	df	p
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE	- AGE	1.543	3	0.221
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE	- SEX	2.857	1	0.214
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE	- ATTENDANCE	2.809	2	0.107
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE	- FAMILY INCOME	2.206	3	0.114

Note. Student's t-test.

The paired sample t-test results in Table 2 show that age, sex, attendance, and family income have no statistically significant effect on the academic performance of Grade 3 Jolly pupils, as all p-values exceed the significance level (SOP = 0.03), with age ($p = 0.221$) and family income ($p = 0.114$) as examples. This indicates that within this sample, academic achievement does not differ based on these demographic factors. The findings suggest that other influences, such as teaching methods, classroom environment, or parental involvement, may play a more important role in student performance. Future studies with larger or more diverse samples could provide further insights into these relationships.

Conclusions

The study concludes that parental involvement has a strong positive relationship with the academic performance of Grade 3 pupils at Old Kibawe Elementary School, although the correlation was not statistically significant. Demographic factors, including age, sex, attendance, and family income, were not significant determinants of student achievement within this sample. These findings indicate that parental engagement alone may not directly determine academic success but supports students' learning experiences and overall motivation.

Moreover, the study underscores that academic performance is shaped by multiple interrelated factors, including instructional practices, learning resources, and home support. Educators, parents, and policymakers should therefore promote sustained parental involvement and develop strategies that leverage home-school collaboration. Future research with larger and more diverse samples is recommended to explore the causal mechanisms linking parental involvement with student achievement and to examine the quality of engagement rather than frequency alone.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proposed:

1. Educators and policymakers should focus on enhancing teaching methods, classroom environment, and psychological support while maintaining opportunities for parental engagement.
2. Teachers should foster home-school partnerships to strengthen parental involvement, while parents should remain active in their children's education.
3. Future research should involve larger, more diverse samples, explore additional academic influences, and examine longitudinal effects of parental engagement.
4. Curriculum planners should design programs to facilitate parental involvement and support effective school-home partnerships.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers adhered to strict ethical guidelines throughout the conduct of this research. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, including parents/guardians of the minor respondents. All respondents were informed of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. The anonymity

and confidentiality of all respondents were maintained; no personal identifiers were included in the data collection or reporting. The well-being and safety of all participants were safeguarded throughout the research process. No conflict of interest existed in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided through proper citation and acknowledgment of all sources. The researcher maintain objectivity in the interpretation of findings, ensuring no bias influenced the results. The data and results obtained were used purely for academic and research purposes only.

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